

CONTEXTUALIZING AND LOCATING PROFESSIONALISM: SOCIAL WORK PRACTICE IN NORTH-EAST INDIA

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Abstract

The introduction and relevance of social work in developing countries such as ours, is often contended and challenged for its professional imperialism. It is against this backdrop that the present paper examines the relevance and adequacy of social work profession in addressing the contemporary needs and challenges in North-East India. The paper explores the dynamics presented by the interaction of social work professionalism, tribal cultural milieu as well as the charity and missionary orientations of Christianity. It addresses issues and concerns of social work practice in this scenario. Further, it identifies the relevance of theoretical perspectives, models, methods and techniques and seeks to answer the question on the adequacy of social work training. It also explores the scope of social work practice in existing institutional and non-institutional settings.

Key Words: Professionalism, Social Workers, Social Work Practice

Introduction

The North-East Region of India comprises of seven contiguous states traditionally.

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It is a region that is distinct from the rest of India in ethnic, geo-political and Socio cultural nature. The eighth state of Sikkim has often been included out of convenience since it shares certain broad similarities in stock and race of people. The strategic importance of the region in India is largely due to the fact that it shares international boundaries with five different countries (Nepal, Bhutan, China, Myanmar and Bangladesh). The region is thus vulnerable to illicit cross-border trade, migration, attacks and transfer of goods and services. The region is also particularly vulnerable as it lies in the conduit of the Golden Triangle for illicit drugs trafficking. The region is known for its rich bio-diversity, heavy rainfall as well as a rich and diverse ethnic culture and is inhabited by tribes, predominantly the Tibeto-Burman tribes. Christianity is a predominant religion in at least three of the seven states in the region.

Mizoram is a young and small state that is best known for the enviable statistics of being the highest in literacy in the country. It shares boundaries with Assam, Tripura and Manipur and shares international boundaries with Myanmar and Bangladesh. The state of Mizoram is inhabited by the people of the Mizo tribe and most people of the state are Christian. Mizo tribal culture had the Zawlbuk (boy's dormitory) where youth were instructed into several Mizo customs and graces. By virtue of the tribal origins, the Mizos are community oriented and spend a large part of their life in sharing and giving. *Tlawmngaihna* best describes the cardinal value of Mizo tribal life and it is loosely translated to mean 'selfless service' somewhat akin to altruism. *Hnatlang* or community service is another tradition of Voluntarism that is deeply embedded in the Mizo way of life. A call for *Hnatlang* will see all Mizo families send atleast one representative to help the larger community, often in providing labour. This spirit of *Hnatlang* sees youth involved in rescuing people in distress, building or laying roads, cleaning the streets, clearing the drain or indeed in rebuilding the house of someone who has had a tragedy. *Hnatlang* and *Tlawmngaihna* are seen by some (Pachau, 2008) as two sides of the same coin and reflective of the spirit of voluntarism. It is in the context of these humanistic values that were already evident in traditional Mizo culture, that Christianity was introduced. Christianity brought education to the Mizos who until then had no script. Therefore all history until a hundred years ago was oral history. Christian Values that were communicated were those values that were taught by Jesus Christ. Worship to God, Marital fidelity, forgiveness and unconditional love were some of the values that were reinforced by the religion. The predominant denomination in the North of Mizoram is that of Presbyterianism while the south of Mizoram has more Baptists. Catholics form a small portion of the overall population. The tribal

tradition of Tlawmgaihna has with the advent of Christianity a hundred years ago, combined to produce a very rich and illustrious tradition of social service in the state. The 'missionary Zeal', Christian traditional Values, community membership that demands one to contribute his/her time, energy and resources for the upliftment of Mizo society and the very strong societal links have contributed to producing socially sensitive citizens (Desai, 2006).

The social problems in this state are quite unique. Socio-economic development in the state is poor despite the very high literacy. Women enjoy high visibility in work and community activities although the Mizo society is a patriarchal society. By virtue of its geographical positioning, Mizoram is vulnerable to problems such as substance abuse and HIV/AIDS. To support the addiction, some female youth have taken to sex work and many youth indulge in multiple sexual relationships compounding problems further. There has been a sharp rise in AIDS mortality figures from 4 cases in 1997 to 75 cases in 2005 (Desai, 2006). The state has several associations and NGOs that are age or gender group oriented (YMA, MHIP, MUP) which address a range of problems and they are predominantly run on the lines of Christian and traditional tribal values. Human rights, gender justice, issues related to empowerment and development are however addressed only by the newer NGOs which are run by (or has the presence of) professional social workers. Often the trained social workers have to address issues of human rights violations by some of the larger traditional NGOs (reference to the 'war against drugs' where some people were mercilessly beaten allegedly by the members of NGOs which wanted to 'clean up the streets' and reduce drug intake by all means).

Professional Social Work Education

It is in this context in which Professional Social Work Education began to be offered in the state in 2002 as a post-millennium course after the formation of the Mizoram University. It would however be erroneous to state that social work as a profession was introduced in the state only this recently. Prior to 2002, there were at least 20-30 social work professionals who were trained in some of the better schools of social work outside the region (viz., TISS, Delhi School of Social Work, University of Pune, Nirmala Niketan etc). These social workers (the first of whom graduated in the mid sixties) were employed in key positions within the state in government departments such as the department of social welfare. None of them had qualified for the UGC NET exam by 2002 when the department of social work began in 2002. The services of some of these experienced social work practitioners was however utilized for a very short period of few months when the

department began to offer social work education. Has professionalism added or detracted from the practice of social work among the Mizos? Mizos are community oriented and have a tradition of social service and voluntarism that is very high. Moreover Mizos are Christians and all their work reflects their values as Christians. Charity and welfare are therefore integral values of the Mizos. Indigenous methods and skills have been developed by the Mizos in addressing their community problems. Professionalism in social work brings with it its own set of values that may be contrary to the ones being practiced by Mizos. Further, the introduction of a theoretical framework of operation, methods and skills by professional social work brings with it a set of standards. How does this get translated in the context of social work in contemporary Mizoram? This is a question being raised in the present paper. The paper addresses the questions raised by professionalism in the context of a tribal state that is predominantly Christian in composition.

Methodology

The present study is cross sectional in nature and descriptive in design. It is based on the primary data collected through social survey with structured questionnaire. The social work professionals who practice social work at least for a period of one year in Aizawl constituted the respondents while the unit of the study being individual. A list of professional social workers in Aizawl was compiled with the help of five professional social workers who were in constant touch with a number of social workers.

All social workers in Aizawl were distributed questionnaires through these five persons. Some of the respondents did not return the questionnaires and only the filled in questionnaires were included in the study.

The collected data was processed and analysed with the help of Ms Excel and SPSS. To analyse the data, apart from simple averages, and percentages, Kendal's concordance (Kendal's W), Kendal tau ordinal correlation coefficients were used. In this study to identify the priority of social work practice issues, models, methods, techniques and skills ranks have been used. To obtain a comprehensive picture, they were transmuted into scores and aggregated at each indicator level using the procedure suggested by Garrett (1966:328-329) with a simple modification* (see Zaitinwawra & Kanagaraj 2008; and Hmar & Kanagaraj 2007).

Results and Discussion

1. Demographic, Social and Economic Profile: A total of 42 social work practitioners were contacted and information was sought from them. Of these 24

(57%) were female and the remaining (43%) were male. A large majority of these practitioners (91%) are youth between the ages of 25-35 years. The remaining are over the age of 35 years. Thus the age profile of the social work practitioners is a young profile. Almost two thirds of the respondents (64%) are unmarried and single; while close to a third (31%) are married. A small number (5%) are divorced. All respondents in this study are Christian and belong to Scheduled tribe status. An overwhelming majority (93%) belong to urban localities while the remaining belonged to rural (2%) and semi-urban residences (5%). The average profile of the social work practitioner in Mizoram is that of a young, urban unmarried, Christian, ST female.

Information on socio-economic status was sought from the respondents and this reveals that almost half the respondents (48%) reported that their fathers had had the benefit of higher education at the time of the post-graduation of the respondents. Correspondingly only 5% reported mothers having had similar educational status at the time of their post-graduation. While only a third (33%) reported that their fathers had studied up to SSLC, more than two-thirds (67%) reported that their mothers had studied only up to SSLC. Information on educational levels of parents at the time of post-graduation of respondents was sought. Almost half the respondents (48%) reported that their fathers had had the benefit of higher education at the time of the post-graduation of the respondents. Correspondingly only 5% reported mothers having had similar educational status at the time of their post-graduation. While only a third (33%) reported that their fathers had studied up to SSLC, more than two-thirds (67%) reported that their mothers had studied only up to SSLC. This is not a very surprising finding since the state has the enviable position of being the second most literate state in the country. A further exploration of the socio-economic status of respondents reveals that more than a quarter of the respondents (26%) reported that their fathers had government jobs and a fifth (20%) had fathers who were government officers while they were doing their post-graduation in social work. More than a quarter (29%) reported that their mothers had government jobs and only one respondent had a mother who was a government officer at the same time. A tenth of the respondents had fathers who played non-traditional roles as Home maker and only 14% had mothers who were home makers. More than a quarter of the respondents (26%) reported that mothers were working as labour. This profile gives us an idea of the sociology of social workers. In Mizoram the course attracts people from a salaried and predominantly middle class stratum in society.

2. Educational Profile: An overwhelming majority of social workers (90%) have completed their graduation in the social sciences. Only a fifth of the social workers have acquired a first class in their graduation while more than two-thirds had obtained a second class. However, interestingly a majority (71%) have a first class degree obtained in post-graduation with one person reporting a distinction. Over half the respondents (55%) have a specialisation in community development and only a fifth (21%) and less than a fifth (17%) reporting Family and child welfare and Medical and Psychiatric social work respectively. Based on the perceived need of specialisation as well as on availability of teaching faculty, the Mizoram University has consistently offered Community development in the first five years of its existence. Other specializations have been offered less frequently. Following 2007, we have begun offering a generic course. Almost two-thirds of the respondents have graduated from Mizoram University. Almost a sixth (14%) have graduated from Pune where all students offer community development as a specialisation and a small minority each from Delhi (5%), TISS (2%), Vidyasagar, Bangalore and Bombay universities. An overwhelming majority (93%) have an MSW degree while the remaining have received an M.A. in social Work.

Again, an overwhelming majority (91%) of respondents have obtained their social work degree after 2000. This is not too surprising since the Mizoram University was founded only in 2001 and the department of social work was started in 2002. Prior to 2000, few people could afford to send their children out of the state for higher education. On professional experience, a great majority (88%) had between 1-5 years of experience while the remaining had over 6 years of experience.

3. Organizational Context: More than a quarter of the respondents (26%) have sought employment with government organizations which include the Directorate of Social Welfare, MSD&RB and MSACS. Almost two-thirds (62%) are with Non-governmental organizations that work on issues related to community development, children, youth and issues such as substance abuse and HIV/AIDS. The remaining are distributed across faith based organisations and private companies that run health care services.

Information on the reach of the organisation and level of operation of the NGO was sought and this reveals that over half of the respondents (52%) have state wide presence while more than a quarter (26%) work at the grassroots level. a small number (14%) report working at the regional level while a very insignificant minority report working at the National (5%) or International level (2%). This is

again not too surprising since networking by NGO's seems to be restricted to within the state and it is only the FBO's that are likely to have networks outside the country.

While all respondents report being Christian and tribal, interestingly the orientation towards religion by them is reported as being secular by a great majority (88%) with just over a tenth (12%) reporting that they are Christian in their orientation. Observations during field work practice and supervision by the department of social work has however consistently revealed that the methods used for problem solving by NGO's is faith based and in several cases spiritual counseling, gospel camps are the main form of solace that is offered even by trained social workers.

A quarter of the respondents (26%) reported that their fathers had government jobs and a fifth (20%) had fathers who were government officers while more than a quarter (29%) reported that their mothers had government jobs and only one respondent had a mother who was a government officer. A tenth of the respondents had fathers who played non-traditional roles as Home maker and only 14% had mothers who were home makers. More than a quarter of the respondents (26%) reported that mothers were working as labour.

4. Social Issues and Service Users of Social Work: Social workers in the developing countries are often criticized for neglecting the real problems and social work is considered as professional imperialism (Midgely, 1981). The question in the context of the North eastern India is: what are the problems that professional social workers address most frequently? To answer this question the social workers were asked to rank a set of social issues that confront Mizoram today in terms of their frequency of intervention. The problems were HIV/AIDS, Poverty, Exclusion & Marginalization, Substance Abuse, Community Health, Child Abuse & Neglect Gender Justice & Equality, Sex Work, Human Rights and Social Justice, Domestic Violence, Disability, Education, Mental Health, Care of Older Persons, and Crime and Correction. For obtaining clear and comprehensive results, the ranks were transmuted into scores using Garrett's (1966) procedure with a modification in aggregation (See Hmar & Kanagaraj 2007; and Zaitinwawra & Kanagaraj 2008). In the Table 6 the transmuted scores and their ranking are presented along with the frequency of respondents who ranked them.

Barring crime and correction and mental health, other issues are addressed by majority of the professional social workers in Mizoram. More than one half of the respondents ranked the issues of HIV/AIDS (76%), Poverty, Exclusion &

Marginalization (69%), Substance Abuse (62%), Community Health (60%), Child Abuse & Neglect (57%), Gender Justice & Equality (57%), Sex Work (55%), Human Rights and Social Justice (57%), Domestic Violence (55%), Disability (55%), Education (55%), and Care of Older Persons (50%). Though the issues of mental health and crime and correction are addressed by a minority they are not addressed by a substantial section of the professionals. Nearly one half of the professionals address the issues of mental health (48%) and crime and correction (45%) in their practice.

The issues of HIV/AIDS, Poverty, Exclusion & Marginalization, and Substance Abuse emerged as the top most priority issues addressed by professional social workers. These issues have obtained the top three ranks from the respondents in terms of interaction.

HIV/AIDS constitutes the top most issue for social work intervention in Mizoram. More than three fourth of the respondents (76%) address this issue. HIV/AIDS secured the first rank of all the 14 issues which were given for ranking with a mean transmuted score of 52. The issue of poverty exclusion and marginalization has secured the second top most issue for social work practice in Mizoram. It was addressed by more than three fourth of the respondents (69%) and its mean transmuted score was computed to be 44. The third issue that acquired the priority of social work practice is substance abuse. More than one half of the respondents address the problem substance abuse (62%) in Mizoram while the mean transmuted score was computed to be 33. Interestingly, the three top most issues frequently encountered by professional social workers are closely related to each other.

Mental health, care of older persons, crime and correction constitute the issues that acquire least attention from the social workers. Mental health secured 12th rank with a mean transmuted score of 23 while care of older persons and crime stood at 13th and 14th positions among the 14 issues listed.

5. Patterns of Professional Social Work Service Use: The respondents were asked to rank four kinds of service users of social work practice in terms of their frequency of encounter. They are the youth, children, adolescents, and older persons. The ranks were transmuted using the procedure suggested by Garret (1962). The aggregate mean scores along with the frequency are presented in Table 6.

Interestingly, a predominant majority of professionals work with all the age groups. More than four fifth of the respondents ranked youth (93%), children (90%), adolescents (86%) and older persons (88%). The order of priority of social

work practice was youth, children, adolescents and older persons.

6. Patterns of Social Work Practice: Models Methods and Skills: Social Work practice in India is often criticized for its orientation towards clinical and curative model as well as for its orientation towards case work method. How far is this true in the context of Mizoram? To answer this question the respondents were asked to rank models, methods, and skills in terms of their frequency of usage in practice. The mean transmuted scores, frequency of respondents ranking and the aggregate ranking are presented in Table 5.

As regards the models, it is interesting to note that a predominant majority of professional social workers in Mizoram use all the models. More than 90 percent of the respondents ranked developmental, preventive, rehabilitative, empowerment, remedial and curative models of social work practice. Of these five models developmental, preventive and rehabilitative models were ranked the first three positions respectively. On the other hand the empowerment, remedial and curative models were ranked the fourth, fifth and sixth positions respectively. It is clear that the development paradigm has gained currency over the welfare models while empowerment model has yet to become the predominant model.

Like all models, all methods are practiced by the social workers in Mizoram. More than four- fifth of the respondents ranked social case work (95%), group work (90%), community practice (93%), social welfare administration (86%), social work research (83%), and social action (88%) while a similar proportion of them use generalist or integrated social work practice (88%).

Social case work, community practice, and social group work secured the top three ranks among the various methods of practice among the professional social workers in Mizoram. The social work professionals in Mizoram most frequently work with individuals and practice social case work. Social case work secured the first rank with a score of 52. The next method in the order was community practice which stood at second rank from the top with mean transmuted score of 49. The third method in the order of frequency of use was social group work with a mean score of 46. On the other hand, the minor methods of social welfare administration, social work research and social action were the least frequently practiced methods.

Social welfare administration secured the fifth rank with a mean transmuted score of 35; social work research secured a mean of 32 while social action secured a mean of 29. Interestingly, generalist practice or integrated social work secured the middle position in the order of frequency of use among social work professionals.

Like the models and methods, all the skills are being used by social work professionals in Mizoram. More than four fifth of the respondents ranked skills such as Recording and Reporting (95%), Networking and Collaboration (93%), Mobilization and Organization (90%), Office Management (98%), Lobbying (88%), Research and Evaluation (88%), Counseling (90%), and Project Formulation (90%). Of these skills, recording and reporting, office management, and networking and collaboration were the three skills most frequently used by social workers in Mizoram. Recording and reporting secured the first rank with a transmuted score of 57. In the second position, office management was placed with a mean transmuted score of 53. Networking and collaboration was placed in the third position with a computed transmuted score of 52. On the other hand, counseling, research and evaluation, and lobbying were placed in the sixth, seven, and eighth ranks in terms of their frequency of use respectively with the mean transmuted scores of 37, 34 and 27. Interestingly, mobilization and organization and project formulation occupied middle positions in the order of frequency of use. Mobilization and organization was ranked to the fourth position with 43 points of mean transmuted score while project formulation was placed in the fifth position with a mean score of 38.

7. Fit between Social Work Issues and Models, Methods and Techniques: The major question that remains unanswered is relevance of social work models, methods and techniques to address the social problems of the region. To answer this question, Kendal tau correlation coefficients were computed between the transmuted scores of the social work models, methods and techniques on the one hand and the social issues addressed by the social workers in Mizoram on the other (see Table 8).

Interestingly, of the six models analyzed, the frequency of application of empowerment model has highest fitness with 5 major issues viz., poverty, social exclusion and marginalization, Human Rights and Social Justice, Child Abuse & Neglect, Gender Justice & Equality as well as HIV/AIDS. Interestingly, the correlation coefficients of empowerment model with the issues of poverty, social exclusion and marginalization (0.3), Human Rights and Social Justice (0.3), Child Abuse & Neglect (0.3), Gender Justice & Equality (0.3) were all positive and significant at 5 percent level while with HIV/AIDS (-0.3) was negative and significant at 5 percent level.

The preventive model of social work practice was found to have fit with four major social issues addressed by social workers in Mizoram. They are Substance

Abuse, Sex Work, HIV/AIDS, and poverty, social exclusion and marginalization. The frequency of practice of social work with the interrelated issues of substance abuse, sex work and HIV/AIDS had significant and positive correlation with the preventive model at 5 percent level. On the other hand, there was a significant and negative correlation observed between the preventive model and social work practice with poverty, social exclusion and marginalization (-0.3).

Remedial, therapeutic, and developmental models were found to have negative fit with at least one of the issues addressed by the social workers in Mizoram. Sex Work has a significant negative correlation with the frequency of remedial model while poverty (-0.3) and Child Abuse & Neglect (-0.3) had significant negative correlation with therapeutic model. On the other hand, developmental model had significant negative correlation with substance abuse (-0.3).

Among the methods, generalist social work as well as social work research was found to have greatest positive fit with specific issues addressed by the social work practice in Mizoram.

Generalist social work or integrated social work has positive fit with the issues of poverty, domestic violence, disability, human rights and social justice, and care of older persons. Similarly, social work research has positive fit with human rights and justice, child abuse and neglect and crime and correction. Social Welfare Administration had a fit with care of older persons while Social Group Work had a positive fit with HIV/AIDS. On the other hand, Social Case Work had negative fit with poverty, exclusion and marginalization. Community practice had negative fit with Mental Health, disability, and sex work.

Among the skills, only three of the eight, research and evaluation, lobbying, and recording reporting as well as project formulation, had positive fit with some the major issues addressed by social workers in Mizoram. Research evaluation was found to be fit with the issues of substance abuse, and sex work. The skill in lobbying was found to be specific fit with domestic violence and gender justice and equality while recording and reporting had a positive fit with community health. Interestingly, the skills of office management had negative fit with the social work practice with the issue of Child Abuse & Neglect.

Fit between Service Users and Models, Methods and Techniques of Social Work

To understand the pattern of fit between social work models, methods and techniques on the one hand and the service users on the other hand is one of the objectives of the study. To accomplish these Kendal tau correlation coefficients

were computed between transmuted scores of the social work models, methods and techniques on the one hand and the service users on the other (Table 9).

Among the models preventive model was found to have positive fit with adolescent and youth while having negative fit with social work with older persons. On the other hand, the remedial model had a positive fit with adolescents while developmental model had a positive fit with older persons. Interestingly, therapeutic/curative, rehabilitative and empowerment models do not have fit with any one specific issue. As regards the methods, only generalist or integrated social work practice had a positive fit with the older persons. Likewise, among the skills and techniques lobbying alone had significant positive fit with children and negative fit with older persons.

Conclusion

The results of the present study clearly demonstrate the high degree of professionalism among the social work practitioners in Mizoram, North East India. It is not only in the application of the models, methods, and techniques but also in responding to the dire challenges of the region and fit between them. We attribute four interrelated and interacting factors responsible for the high degree of professionalism embedded in practice. They are the Christianized tribal socio cultural milieu, formalized Mizo social structure with emergent middle class in stratification, presence of social work professionals in the state bureaucracy, dominance of professionals in voluntary sector with professional aspiration (Ralte & Kanagaraj, 2007) and social work education promoted by the Mizoram University. While professionalism has been introduced by social workers in the government and voluntary sector, the earlier traditions of charity and welfare of the NGOs and faith based organizations continues. In other words, professionalism has not replaced traditional approaches and instead both seem to work parallelly and co-exist. Similarly, the *hnatlang* and *tlawmngaihna* concepts are deeply embedded in the collective psyche and this spirit of voluntarism is evident in all Mizo youth. The dynamics of this co-existence of professionalism introduced by social workers in some organizations and the faith based work of other NGOs remain to be addressed through further research.

In spite of this high degree of professionalism, social workers in Mizoram have to address a number of challenges. There are challenges of sustainability, access and effectiveness. The professionals are by and large young and their experience in the field is too little. The question here is how long they will maintain their enthusiasm, which is almost always associated with age. In the department of

social work, we have seen this enthusiasm of young students at both entry and departing points of social work education. We have understood it as related to their Christian traditions of having a 'missionary zeal' as well as their Mizo tribal origins of wanting to work for the betterment of their community. Secondly, social work in Mizoram is still an urban phenomenon and it has to reach the nook and corner of Mizoram where the problems of poverty, exclusion, drug use and the threat of AIDS/HIV are significant. Thirdly, a big challenge is that of effectiveness. The question of how far social work models, methods, techniques are effective in achieving the goals of social welfare, development and empowerment and eradicating poverty exclusion, ill health and illiteracy still remains unanswered. We hope social work educators and practitioners in the region will address these issues in a conscious manner through education, research, collaboration and networking among themselves. In addition it is imperative to network at regional, national, and global levels among the agencies of state as well as civil society.

Table 1: Demographic Social and Economic Profile

Sl.No		Frequency	Percent
I	Gender		
	Female	24	57
	Male	18	43
II	Age Group		
	Below 25 Years	2	5
	25 - 35 Years	36	86
	35 Years and Above	4	10
	<i>Mean Age</i>	29.47 + 6.46	
III	Marital Status		
	Unmarried	27	64
	Married	13	31
	Divorced	2	5
IV	Community		
	ST	42	100
V	Religion		
	Christian	42	100
VI	Locality		
	Rural	1	2

	Urban	39	93
	Semi-Urban	2	5
VII	Father' Education		
	No Response	2	5
	SSLC and Below	14	33
	Higher Secondary	6	14
	Higher Education	20	48
VIII	Mother's Education		
	No Response	2	5
	SSLC and Below	28	67
	Higher Secondary	10	24
	Higher Education	2	5
IX	Father's Occupation		
	Home Maker	4	10
	Cultivator	3	7
	Petty Business	9	21
	Professional	3	7
	Government Servant	11	26
	Government Officer	8	19
	Large Business/ Contractor	4	10
X	Mother's Occupation		
	Home Maker	6	14
	Labour	11	26
	Cultivator	3	7
	Petty Business	8	19
	Government Servant	12	29
	Government Officer	1	2
	Large Business/ Contractor	1	2

Source: Computed

Table 2: Educational Profile of Professional Social Workers

Sl.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
I	Subject of Bachelor Degree		
	Social Sciences	38	90
	Natural Sciences	4	10

II	Class in BSW/BA/BSC		
	First Class	9	21
	Second Class	28	67
	Third Class	5	12
III	Professional Education		
	MSW 39	93	
	MA(SW)	3	7
IV	Specialization		
	Generic	3	7
	Community Development (CD)	23	55
	Family and Child Welfare(FCW)	9	21
	Medical and Psychiatric Social Work	7	17
V	Class in MSW/MA		
	Distinction	1	2
	First Class	30	71
	Second Class	11	26
VI	University		
	Bangalore	1	2
	Bombay	1	2
	Delhi 2	5	
	Madurai Kamaraj	1	2
	Madras	2	5
	Mizoram	27	64
	Pune 6	14	
	TISS 1	2	
	Vidyasagar	1	2
VII	Year of Award of MSW/MA		
	1979 1	2	
	1985 1	2	
	1987 1	2	
	2000 1	2	
	2003 4	10	
	2004 5	12	
	2005 7	17	
	2006 11	26	

	2007 11	26	
VIII	Additional Qualification		
	None 38	90	
	M.A 1	2	
	PG Diploma	1	2
	Diploma	1	2
	Certificate	1	2

Source: Computed

Table 3: Organisational Context of Social Work

Sl.No	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
I	Type of Organization		
	Government Organisation	11	26
	Non-Governmental Organisation	26	62
	Faith Based Organisation	2	5
	Private Company	3	7
II	Locus of Operation		
	Grassroots	11	26
	State 22	52	
	Regional	6	14
	National	2	5
	International	1	2
III	Orientation towards religion		
	Christian	5	12
	Secular	37	88
IV	Rank in the Organizational Hierarchy		
	Not Applicable	4	10
	1	4	10
	2	16	38
	3	12	29
	4	6	14

Source: Computed

Table 4: Professional Experience in Government and NGO Contexts

Sl.No	Professional Experience	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	S.D
I	Government	0	28	2.1	5.9
II	Voluntary Organizations	0	8.6	1.9	1.8
III	International Organizations	0	2	0.1	0.4
IV	Total Professional Experience	0.0	28.0	4.1	5.7
	Duration	Frequency	Percent		
	1 - 5 Years	37	88		
	6 -9 Years	1	2		
	10 Years and Above	4	10		

Source: Computed

Table 5: Motivation for Joining Social Work Course: Order of Factors

Sl.No	Factor	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D	Rank
1	Commitment to Social Welfare	31	73.81	41.0	27.4	1
2	Influence of Peers, Seniors, Friends or Relatives	22	52.38	27.8	28.7	2
3	Religious or Missionary Orientation	18	42.86	18.9	25.0	3
4	Assured Employment	17	40.48	18.0	23.5	4
5	High Social Status	18	42.86	11.8	18.6	5
6	Higher Income	14	33.33	6.4	13.5	6
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.26				
	Chi-Square	55.47**				
	df	5				

Source: Computed

**Table 6: Social Issues and Service Users of Social Work:
Order of Frequency of Intervention**

Sl.No		Frequency	Percent	Transmuted Score		Rank
				Mean	S.D	
I	Social Issues					
	HIV/AIDS	32	76	52	31.0	1
	Poverty, Exclusion & Marginalisation	29	69	44	35.2	2
	Substance Abuse	26	62	39	33.1	3
	Community Health	25	60	37	32.3	4
	Child Abuse & Neglect	24	57	32	30.3	5
	Gender Justice & Equality	24	57	31	29.0	6
	Sex Work	23	55	30	32.1	7
	Human Rights and Social Justice	24	57	29	28.7	8
	Domestic Violence	23	55	28	28.2	9
	Disability	23	55	27	28.4	10
	Education	23	55	26	29.7	11
	Mental Health	20	48	23	26.8	12
	Care of Older Persons	21	50	18	25.3	13
	Crime and Correction	19	45	17	24.2	14
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.14				
Chi-Square	79.03**					
Df	13.00					
Asymp. Sig.	0.00					
II	Service Users					
	Youth	39	93	47	20.4	1
	Children	38	90	38	22.8	2
	Adolescents	36	86	38	20.0	3
	Older Persons	37	88	18	27.4	4
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.13				
	Chi-Square	16.98**				
	Df	3.00				
	Asymp. Sig.	0.00				

Source: Computed

* P<0.05

** P<0.01

**Table 7: Social Work Models Methods and Techniques in Practice:
Order of Frequency of Application**

Sl.No	Social Work	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D	Rank
I	Models					
	Developmental	40	95	47.1	20.0	1
	Preventive	41	98	44.8	24.7	2
	Rehabilitative	41	98	41.9	22.1	3
	Empowerment	40	95	41.0	24.0	4
	Remedial	40	95	36.6	22.1	5
	Therapeutic/Curative	40	95	32.2	24.3	6
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.05				
	Chi-Square	10.39				
	Df	5				
	Asymp. Sig.	0.06				
II	Methods					
	Social Case Work	40	95	51.55	23.09	1
	Community Practice/ Organization	39	93	49.14	22.88	2
	Social Group Work	38	90	46.02	19.67	3
	Generalist Social Work - Integrated Social Work	37	88	41.31	26.54	4
	Social Welfare Administration	36	86	35.29	22.69	5
	Social Work Research	35	83	32.48	25.55	6
	Social Action	37	88	29.17	23.76	7
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.14				
	Chi-Square	35.63**				
	Df	6				
	Asymp. Sig.	0.00				
III	Skills and Techniques					
	Project Formulation	38	90	38.31	25.85	1
	Counseling	38	90	36.76	25.47	2
	Research and Evaluation	37	88	34.36	25.46	3
	Lobbying	37	88	27.19	23.77	4

	Office Management	41	98	53.26	22.04	5
	Mobilization and Organization	38	90	43.48	19.54	6
	Networking and Collaboration	39	93	51.76	18.28	7
	Recording and Reporting	40	95	56.74	16.15	8
	Test Statistics					
	Kendall's W	0.19				
	Chi-Square	56.19**				
	Df	7				
	Asymp. Sig.	0.00				

Source: Computed

* P<0.05

** P<0.01

Table 8: Relevance of and Fit between Social Work Issues and Practice: Kendal Tau

Sl.No	Dimensions of Practice	Social Work Issues													
		I01	I02	I03	I04	I05	I06	I07	I08	I09	I10	I11	I12	I13	I14
I	Models of Social Work														
	Remedial	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1	-0.3*	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.2	-0.1
	Preventive	-0.3*	0.1	0.3*	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.3*	0.6**	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.1
	Therapeutic/Curative	-0.3*	-0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	-0.1	-0.3*	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
	Rehabilitative	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.1	0.3*	-0.1	-0.3*	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1
	Developmental	0.2	0.1	-0.4**	-0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0
	Empowerment	0.3*	0.2	-0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	-0.3*	0.0	0.3*	0.3*	0.0	0.1	0.3*
II	Methods														
	Social Case Work	-0.3*	-0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	-0.1
	Social Group Work	-0.2	-0.2	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3*	0.0	-0.2	-0.2	-0.2	0.0	-0.2
	Community Practice/ Organization	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3*	-0.2	-0.3*	-0.3*	0.0	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	-0.2	-0.2	-0.1
	Social Action	-0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.2	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.2
	Social Welfare Administration	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.2	-0.1	0.3*	0.0	0.0
	Social Work Research	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.2	-0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.3*	0.3*	0.0	0.3*	0.1
	Generalist Social Work/ Integrated Social Work	0.3*	0.3*	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3*	0.2	-0.1	0.2	0.3*	0.1	0.4*	0.2	0.1
III	Techniques														
	Counseling	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
	Recording and Reporting	0.0	-0.2	-0.1	-0.1	0.3*	-0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.2	0.0	-0.1	-0.1
	Office Management	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	-0.1	-0.1	-0.3*	-0.1	0.0	-0.1
	Networking and Collaboration	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	-0.1	0.2	0.0	-0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1
	Lobbying	0.0	0.3*	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3*
	Mobilization and Organization	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.2
	Research and Evaluation	0.0	0.0	0.3*	0.1	0.1	-0.1	0.3*	0.2	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1
	Project Formulation	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.4**

Source: Computed

* P<0.05

** P<0.01

I01 Poverty, Exclusion & Marginalisation; I02 Domestic Violence; I03 Substance Abuse I04 Mental Health; I05 Community Health; I06 Disability; I07 Sex Work; I08 HIV/AIDS; I09 Education; I10 Human Rights and Social Justice; I11 Child Abuse & Neglect; I12 Care of Older Persons; I13 Crime and Correction; I14 Gender Justice & Equality

**Table 9: Service Users and Social Work Practice:
Kendal Tau Correlation Matrix**

Sl.No	Social Work Models /Methods/ Skills	Service Users			
		Children	Adolescents	Youth	Older Persons
I	Models				
	Remedial	0.2	0.3*	-0.2	-0.1
	Preventive	-0.1	0.5**	0.4**	-0.5**
	Therapeutic/Curative	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0
	Rehabilitative	0.1	-0.2	-0.1	0.2
	Developmental	0.1	-0.1	-0.1	0.3*
	Empowerment	0.1	-0.2	0.0	0.2
II	Methods				
	Social Case Work	0.1	0.2	-0.1	0.0
	Social Group Work	-0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0
	Community Practice/ Organization	0.0	0.1	0.0	-0.1
	Social Action	0.1	0.0	0.0	-0.1
	Social Welfare Administration	0.2	0.2	-0.1	0.0
	Social Work Research	0.0	0.2	0.2	-0.2
	Generalist Social Work - Integrated Social Work	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.3*
III	Techniques				
	Counseling	0.2	0.1	-0.2	0.0
	Recording and Reporting	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1
	Office Management	0.0	0.1	0.2	-0.1
	Networking and Collaboration	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.1
	Lobbying	0.3*	0.1	0.2	-0.3*
	Mobilization and Organization	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0
	Research and Evaluation	0.0	0.2	0.2	-0.1
	Project Formulation	-0.1	-0.1	0.2	0.1

Source: Computed

* P<0.05

** P<0.01

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